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Received: 11 January, 2018

Accepted: 12 February, 2018

Published: 15 February, 2018

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Clinical Image

Saturated Spectroscopy and Unsaturated Spectroscopy Comparative Study on Malignant and Benign Human Cancer Cells and Tissues with the Passage of Time under Synchrotron Radiation

Image Article

In the current study, we have experimentally and comparatively investigated and compared malignant human cancer cells and tissues before and after irradiating of synchrotron radiation using Saturated Spectroscopy and Unsaturated Spectroscopy, respectively. It is clear that malignant human cancer cells and tissues have gradually transformed to benign human cancer cells and tissues under synchrotron radiation with the passage of time (Figures 1,2) [1–163]. It should be noted that malignant human cancer cells and tissues were exposed under white synchrotron radiation for 30 days. Furthermore, there is a shift of the spectrum in all of spectra after irradiating of synchrotron radiation that it is because of the malignant human cancer cells and tissues shrink post white synchrotron irradiation with the passage of time. In addition, all of the figures are related to the same

Figure 1: Saturated Spectroscopy analysis of malignant human cancer cells and tissues. (a) before and (b) after irradiating of synchrotron radiation in transformation process to benign human cancer cells and tissues with the passage of time [1–163].

Figure 2: Unsaturated Spectroscopy analysis of malignant human cancer cells and tissues. (a) before and (b) after irradiating of synchrotron radiation in transformation process to benign human cancer cells and tissues with the passage of time [1–163].

human cancer cells and tissues. Moreover, in all of the figures y-axis shows intensity and also x-axis shows energy (keV).

It can be concluded that malignant human cancer cells and tissues have gradually transformed to benign human cancer cells and tissues under synchrotron radiation with the passage of time (Figures 1,2) [1–163].

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